

CONDUCTING EFL CLASSES BY CONTEMPORARY METHODOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

In proportion to the number of people, the number of techniques has also increased. However, each of the methods has both pros and cons. The operating principles of the old school are subject to sharp criticism today, despite the fact that the use of "classics" brought results, and considerable ones. The only question is at what cost were these results achieved? Typically, in order to master a language, I had to pore over books for a long time, devoting a lot of time to translating, reading texts, memorizing new words, performing various exercises and retelling. To change activities it was suggested tasks such as writing essays or dictations. One of the oldest techniques is classical or fundamental.

Key words: English as a foreign language, communication, interactive teaching methods.

The purpose of the classical method is not so much study as understanding the intricacies and details of the principles of a foreign language. The main task that pursued by the classical method is the formation of the grammatical base of the language being studied. The target audience is people starting to learn English from scratch, from the basics. This technique very familiar to those who started learning English at school. It is worth noting that it is she who is given preference for many language universities, both in Uzbekistan and in other countries. Simplified diagram is the study of grammar, the basic rules that are subsequently applied in specific examples and reinforced with exercises. Her famous "Bonk textbook", co-authored with other representatives of the same traditional methodology, is a kind of template. This tutorial has withstood fierce competition with the latest techniques coming from the West, and continue remain the standard. The only drawback, or rather, even a drawback of the classical method is an important experience of spoken language. This deficiency can be compensated by adding classical methods and other methods of communicative teaching. One of these methods I called linguo-sociocultural method. Supporters of the above method are those who believe that a modern foreign language should not be a set of lexical and grammatical rules. On the contrary, the absence of extra-linguistic factors leads to the fact that learning English becomes boring and aimless. Adherents of the linguo-sociocultural method erect a foreign language as a communicative tool that helps a person not only speak, but also gives the opportunity for self-expression. Following the principles of the linguo-sociocultural method, one can boldly declare that a foreign language is a kind of mirror in which the way of life is reflected life, traditions and customs, culture and history of language. This technique has proven itself well in America and Europe. Continuing to conquer the world, the communicative technique has come to us, taking pride of place in

leading language universities of the republic. The technique is based on the integration of two main methods teaching foreign languages: traditional and modern. As the name suggests, important the role in the communicative methodology is given to communication. This technique is to overcome the language barrier. The main thing is to rid a person of fear of in a foreign language, from the fear of speaking a foreign language and at the same time developing other language skills and skills, in particular oral and written speech, reading, listening.

The principle is this: first, students learn and memorize language formulas, expressions, phrases and only then they analyze grammatical structures found in memorized phrases. In simple terms, the principle of oral advance applies. About the fact that there is a special place in communicative methodology is occupied by the practice of communication, as the name itself says. The communicative technique is aimed at development of skills and abilities of speaking a foreign language. Methodology directly affects the structure of the lesson. Very often in classes it is necessary to use game situations, conduct group work, develop tasks to find errors, on the ability to compare and contrast. As a rule, such classes force you to work actively not only memory, but also logic, which allows you to develop the ability to think analytically and figuratively and, in turn, encourages the expression of thoughts. Today, the development of the modern IT industry makes it possible to learning English, the latest interactive resources: latest generation computers, Internet, TV programs, newspapers, magazines. It is very important to put all of the above into practice. This helps to awaken students' interest in the history, culture, and traditions of the country.

The language being studied and helps build skills that will be needed in the future. Education - this is an active interaction between teacher and students, and it cannot be one-sided. It depends on the teacher how successful the learning process will be. It's obvious that everyone. The teacher is guided in accordance with his personal experience in choosing methods and techniques of work. Phonetic charging does not and cannot have a fixed place on lesson. Her place in class depends on the sequence of completing those tasks where students may encounter phonetic difficulties. Phonetic exercise helps to anticipate and avoid them. It is often performed at the beginning lesson, introducing students into its atmosphere, neutralizing the influence of sound environments in their native language. Phonetic charging may precede reading, then it occurs on the material of the text for reading, from which phonetic difficulties are identified and grouped accordingly image and are then offered to students for conscious imitation. In some cases, it may be recommended to start lessons with short phonetic exercises regularly.

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